

First records of the invasive plant *Carpobrotus edulis* from the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast

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Abstract: First observations in Bulgaria of *Carpobrotus edulis* from both sand dunes and coastal cliffs are presented in the current study. In 2024, first signs of naturalisation of *C. edulis*, a species with high potential for invasiveness, were registered on two locations on the Southern Black Sea Coast: in embryonic shifting dunes, on a small beach west of Chernomorets Town, and on a coastal cliff in the town of Ravda. Images of the most significant morphological characteristics, that distinguish *C. edulis* from *C. acinaciformis*, are presented. In 2025, a field survey, monitoring of invasive plants, was carried out at 23 dune systems from the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast and *Carpobrotus* species were not registered in the sand dune habitats of the studied dune complexes. Nevertheless, collected data shows, that unregulated ornamental planting is a major source of propagules for several invasive species in the dune habitats, and the appearance of *Carpobrotus edulis* as a garden escapee from gardens established around hotels, bungalows, beach bars, etc., is a matter of time, given that the species is widely used for ornamental purposes in the area. Therefore, monitoring of priority areas (coastal dunes and cliffs) and timely action by management authorities is needed to eradicate the recorded populations and raise awareness among the local community about the high invasiveness of the species and the existing ecological risk to coastal habitats – sand dunes and coastal cliffs.

Keywords: alien plant invasion, coastal cliffs, Hottentots-fig, psammo- and hasmophytic vegetation, sand dune habitats, western Pontic coast

Introduction

The genus *Carpobrotus* belongs to *Aizoaceae* – the largest family of leaf succulent plants (Hartmann, 1993, 2002). *Carpobrotus* species are mat-forming trailing succulent perennial herbs, most species in the genus are native to South Africa (Wisura & Glen, 1993), where they commonly occur in coastal habitats among other succulent species (Mucina et al., 2006), and are also part of the Fynbos vegetation – a sclerophyllous shrubland characteristic for the Cape Floral Region (Manning, 2018). *Carpobrotus* spp. have been documented from all five continents and are widely naturalised in coastal habitats outside their native range. In Europe two hybridising taxa, *C.*

edulis and *C. acinaciformis*, are widely distributed along the Mediterranean coast from Spain to Greece and along the Atlantic coast from Gibraltar to the United Kingdom (Campoy et al., 2018).

Coastal habitats provide valuable ecosystem services (Van Dijk, 1989; Petrosillo et al., 2007; Haller et al., 2011; Doody, 2013; Drius et al., 2019a, b), but at the same time they are also among the most threatened (Schlacher et al., 2007; Defeo et al., 2009; Malavasi et al., 2014; Janssen et al., 2016). The structure and functions of coastal ecosystems have been severely modified by constantly growing touristic pressure, habitat loss, land-use change and invasive species (Delbaere, 1998; Alados et al., 2004; Hesp & Martínez, 2007; Malavasi et al., 2013; Šilc et al., 2020). The

Fig. 1. Map of the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast with marked two sites with registration of *Carpobrotus edulis* (in red) and 23 studied dune systems (in green).

introduction of alien invasive plants is one of the most significant threats to local biodiversity and natural ecosystems' preservation, as they produce a decline of native taxa and damage native communities (Mack et al., 2000; Gaertner et al., 2009; Simberloff et al., 2013).

Therefore, studies on their impact on coastal habitats, with an emphasis on sand dunes, have increased recently (Campos et al., 2004; Acosta et al., 2008; Carboni et al., 2010; Asensi et al., 2016; Giulio et al., 2021; etc.).

Carpobrotus has been grown in Europe for ornamental purposes since the late seventeenth century (Preston & Sell, 1988). By the end of the nineteenth century there already are records of naturalised populations (Davey, 1909; Lousley, 1971; McClintock, 1975), most probably as a result of propagule escapes from private botanical gardens and from the horticultural industry (Campoy et al., 2018). Another possible scenario for the establishment of certain populations, apart from gardening, might be the deliberate release of the species for soil and sand dune stabilisation (Preston & Sell, 1988). Due to their intense vegetative clonality and the use of stolons as storage organs, a high phenotypic plasticity, resistance to high concentration of salinity, etc., *Carpobrotus* species show strong adaptability and dispersion ability in a wide range of environmental conditions, with a preferential for coastal habitats, both on rocky and sandy coasts (Roiloa et al., 2010, 2017; Roiloa, 2019; Sarmati et al., 2019). Nowadays, *C. edulis* and *C. acinaciformis* are considered among the most widespread and aggressive invasive plants along the Mediterranean coasts (Vilà et al., 2006; Traveset et al., 2008; Carranza et al., 2010; Jucker et al., 2013; Innangi et al., 2023), and most authors agree on their negative influence on growth, survival, germination and reproduction of native species (Conser & Connor, 2009; Santoro et al., 2012; Novoa et al., 2013, 2014a; Sarmati et al., 2019).

In the current study first observations for Bulgaria of *Carpobrotus edulis* from both sand dunes and coastal cliffs are discussed, along with some taxonomical aspects and identification issues and the species' potential for negative ecological impact as a prominent invasive plant in Europe (Campoy et al., 2018).

Methods

In November 2024, during field work on dune habitats mapping, applying the Standard Dune Mapping Procedure for the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast (Prodanov et al., 2025), first signs of naturalisation of *Carpobrotus edulis* were registered at a couple of locations on the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast: (1). Atia Beach, west of Chernomorets Town, Sozopol Municipality, Burgas District; (2) Scalichkite Beach in Ravda Town, Nesebar Municipality, Burgas District. Subsequently, during May – September 2025, a field survey, monitoring of invasive plants in coastal dune habitats, was carried out using both transect

method (in all present dune habitats) and phytosociological plots (5 m × 5 m). Data were collected from 23 dune systems from the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast (from north to south: Chernomorets, Campsite Gradina and Zlatna Ribka, Sozopol – Harmani, Kavatsi – Smokinya, Alepu, Arkutino, Ropotamo, Primorsko – Perla, Primorsko – South, Atliman, Kiten, Koral and Campsite Yug, Lozenets, Oasis, Arapya, Tsarevo – Popski Plazh, Nestinarka, Ahtopol, Veleka, Butamyata, Lipite, Listi, Silistar; Fig. 1).

Due to the importance of land–sea circulation systems, the Bulgarian Black Sea coastline is a separate climatic region within the Continental-Mediterranean climatic zone. Warm summers and mild winters (with positive January temperatures) are typical (700 mm, 4 °C, town of Tsarevo) (Velev, 2002).

Carpobrotus species identification follows Preston & Sell (1988), Gonçalves (1990), Wisura & Glen (1993), Strid & Tan (1997), Cabello (2009), Campoy et al. (2018), Mifsud (2021). Sand dune habitat was defined according to Kavrakova et al. (2009), Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats – EUR28 (2013), Tzonev (2015a, b).

For the precise species identification, following Mifsud (2021), we prepared representative photographs of: (1) developed leaves (three or more nodes below the flower or apical leaves), (2) cross-sections of leaves, (3) base of leaves with a subhyaline (wax-white) swollen lip, (4) abaxial side of flower with calyx lobes, (5) transversal section of flower with petals, stamens and ovary, (6) fruit, (7) cross-section of ovaries (mature flowers or young fruit). All pictures were taken *ex situ* over a 1 × 1 cm grid mat (Fig. 2A–G). Photographs of the whole plants from both locations were also taken *in situ*. Sample material was collected from the location in Ravda Town.

Results and discussion

Taxonomic complexity and identification of *Carpobrotus edulis*

Carpobrotus edulis (L.) N.E.Br., 1926; Basionym: *Mesembryanthemum edule* L., 1759; Order *Caryophyllales* Juss. ex Bercht. & J.Presl; Family: *Aizoaceae* Martinov, Subfamily *Ruschioideae*

Mat-forming trailing succulent perennial herb with opposite leaves, straight or slightly curved, more or less

Fig. 2. Images of the most significant morphological characters of *Carpobrotus edulis*: A. leaves, widest part is in the lower (proximal) half of the leaf; B. cross-section of leaf – equilateral; C. leaves, a subhyaline (wax-white) swollen lip is visible at the base of the leaves; D. abaxial side of a mature flower showing unequal calyx lobes; E. transversal section of a mature flower; F. young fruit; G. cross-section of ovaries of young fruit, number of locules 9–10. Photography M. Valcheva.

connate at the base, sharply 3-angled, with equilateral triangular cross-section (Fig. 2A–C). Leaf color variable, usually bright green. Widest part of leaves in

the lower (proximal) half. A swollen subhyaline (wax-white) lip, at least 1 mm thick, is present on the adaxial surface at the base of leaves, embracing the stem (Fig.

Fig. 3. *Carpobrotus edulis* in embryonic shifting dunes in Atia Beach (20 November 2024). Photography M. Valcheva.

2C). Each pedicel bears a pair of leaf-like bracts, usually positioned near the midpoint. Calyx consists of five unequal lobes (Fig. 2D), the longest 30–70 (80) mm and the shortest 10–35 mm. Flowers are pedicellate, terminal, solitary, up to 120–150 mm in diameter. *C. edulis* var. *edulis* has yellow petals, fading to pink when aging, and *C. edulis* var. *rubescens* has purple petals (Fig. 2E). The receptacle is turbiniform, 20–40 mm long, tapering linearly towards the pedicel. Fruit is fleshy, pulpy, indehiscent and without valves (Fig. 2F), containing numerous glossy, brown, obovoid and slightly compressed seeds. Ovaries normally with 9–10 (11) locules (Fig. 2G).

According to Campoy et al. (2018), a full review of the genus *Carpobrotus* is needed, due to several taxonomic uncertainties. The taxonomy of the two invasive species from the genus in Europe (*C. edulis* and *C. acinaciformis*) has long been debated: e.g. the primary diagnostic character in the original descriptions – petal colour (yellow in *C. edulis*, purple in *C. acinaciformis*) (Wisura & Glen, 1993), has proven unreliable, since several authors have reported a purple-perianth variety of *C. edulis* (*C. edulis* var. *rubescens*) (Preston & Sell, 1988; Strid & Tan, 1997), which is commonly used in horticulture (Cullen, 2011). Hybridisation between *C. edulis* and *C. acinaciformis*

(Ortiz et al., 2008; Andreu et al., 2010; Suehs et al., 2004a, b) further complicates species identification. In several studies and identification keys (Marloth, 1913; Gonçalves, 1990; Cabello, 2009; Mifsud, 2021), leaf cross-section is considered a diagnostic character (an equilateral triangle for *C. edulis*, isosceles for *C. acinaciformis*). According to Wisura and Glen (1993) the receptacle is also an important character in this genus, turbiniform and tapering into the pedicel in *C. edulis*, while not tapering into the pedicel in *C. acinaciformis*. Mifsud (2021) reports a strong and constant morphological character, which distinguishes both species: the base of most leaves of *C. edulis* is furnished with a subhyaline (wax-white) swollen lip embracing the stem, whereas in *C. acinaciformis* it is flat or very slightly raised above the adaxial surface of the leaf.

Habitat characteristics and site conditions of established locations

Carpobrotus edulis was found in two locations on the Southern Black Sea Coast (Fig 1).

First location is Atia Beach west of Chernomorets Town (coordinates: 42°26'43.78"N, 27°34'26.87"E),

Fig. 4. Atia Beach near the town of Chernomorets, Sozopol Municipality, where *Carpobrotus edulis* was registered (place marked with red arrow). Photography B. Prodanov.

where the species was registered in embryonic shifting dunes as part of a characteristic psammophytic community (Fig. 3). Although the habitat is under strong anthropogenic (touristic) pressures like trampling, building of different infrastructure, maintenance of beach areas for tourism and recreation, etc., a good number of typical psammophytes, such as: *Salsola ruthenica*, *Cakile maritima* subsp. *euxina*, *Lactuca tatarica*, *Polygonum maritimum*, *Leymus racemosus* subsp. *sabulosus*, *Eryngium maritimum*, *Glaucium flavum*, *Medicago marina*, were registered in the phytocoenoses. The total vegetation cover was low (5–10%), and the projective cover of typical species varied between 30–40% of the total vegetation cover. In addition to the typical species for embryonic shifting dunes, some species with wider distribution, that are often found on coastal dunes, were also part of the phytocoenoses: *Suaeda maritima*, *S. altissima*, *Cynanchum acutum*, *Atriplex* spp., as well as some anthropophytes and ruderals like *Cynodon dactylon*

and *Tribulus terrestris*. Except from *Carpobrotus edulis* three other invasive alien plants were registered: *Xanthium italicum*, *Opuntia engelmannii* and *Amorpha fruticosa*, posing a significant threat to the psammophytic vegetation. The most probable reason for the establishment of both *Carpobrotus edulis* and *Opuntia engelmannii* is their use for ornamental purposes in the area right behind the narrow strip of embryonic shifting dunes, where various gardening attempts were visible around the bungalows (Fig. 4).

Second location, where *Carpobrotus edulis* was found, is a coastal cliff in the town of Ravda (coordinates: 42°38'17.99"N, 27°40'42.09"E) (Fig. 5) within a small, pocket-type beach (Scalichkite Beach) bordered by a steep limestone cliff (Fig. 6). The cliff reaches a height of approximately 11 m and forms a pronounced rocky backshore, directly controlling sediment accumulation and limiting beach width. The beach is narrow, with an average width of approximately 18–22 m and a total surface area of about

Fig. 5. *Carpobrotus edulis* on a coastal cliff in Scalichkite Beach in Ravda Town (20 November 2024). Photography M. Valcheva.

1199,8 m², with a gently sloping profile of a weakly developed accumulative zone. The species was growing at the base of the cliff, within the impact range of the salt spray, which is not surprising given the high tolerance of *Carpobrotus* species to salinity

(Weber & D'Antonio, 1999; Novoa et al., 2014b; Varone et al., 2017). In this micro-beach, along with *Carpobrotus edulis*, there are also *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Opuntia engelmannii*, *Yucca filamentosa*, as well as other members of the Aizoaceae family, such

Fig. 6. Scalichkite Beach in Ravda Town, where *Carprobrotus edulis* was registered (place marked with red arrow). Orthophoto mosaic B. Prodanov.

as *Mesembryanthemum cordifolium* and *Delosperma cooperi*. There are also photographs (Fig. 7) of the creation of this place as an “art garden in situ”, which is a de facto “release into nature” in order to increase

the decorative value of the landscape, without taking into account the invasiveness of the planted species. No natural chasmophyte vegetation has been registered on the rock around the naturalised plant. A

Fig. 7. “Art garden in situ” on a coastal cliff in Scalichkite Beach in Ravda Town (2022). Source: Google Earth.

partial process of “escape” of these species can also be assumed, since in the landscaping of gardens around hotels and private homes in the immediate vicinity, these species are present.

Post-detection monitoring and implications for invasion risk

After the two registrations in 2024 of this highly invasive species, in 2025 a full inventory of 23 dune systems from the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast (Fig. 1) was carried out during a field survey, concerning invasive plants in coastal dune habitats, on the project KP-06-H84/5-16.12.2024 “Mapping and Spatiotemporal Analysis of Beach-Dune Systems on the Southern Bulgarian Black Sea Coast: Evolution, Anthropogenic Pressure, and Ecological Risks to Dune Habitats”. Fortunately, *Carpobrotus* had not yet been found in the sand dune habitats of the studied dune systems. Nevertheless, data collected during the survey shows, that unregulated ornamental planting is a major source of propagules for several

invasive species in the studied sand dune habitats and the appearance of *Carpobrotus edulis* as a garden escapee from gardens, established around hotels, bungalows, beach bars, etc., is a matter of time, given that the species is widely used for ornamental purposes in the area (e.g. the closely related *Delosperma cooperi*, fortunately not an invasive species, was registered in a couple of locations planted in gardens in the immediate vicinity of the dune habitats: Arapyra, coordinates: 42°11'23.16"N, 27°50'10.05"E, Sozopol – Harmani, coordinates: 42°24'35.95"N, 27°42'10.62"E). Awareness should be raised among the local community, about the invasive character of the species and its ecological impact on coastal habitats in other parts of the world. Growing some plants with invasive potential, like some species of *Carpobrotus*, *Opuntia*, *Sedum*, *Yucca* etc., in vulnerable coastal areas, would facilitate a potential invasion in the natural habitats, therefore, the use for ornamental purposes of such species should be regulated, particularly when such valuable and endangered habitats are concerned (Valcheva et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The spread of *C. edulis* outside its natural range does not seem to be limited by Mediterranean climatic limits, as it occurs in Northwestern France, Southern Great Britain, Ireland and Northern Germany (Campoy et al., 2018), and given current climate change trends, the potential climatic area suitable for the species could easily increase. These first data on naturalised *C. edulis* in coastal habitats in Bulgaria, discussed in the present study, should focus the attention of responsible institutions for the rapid eradication of invasive populations and trigger monitoring of priority areas (coastal dunes and cliffs) and awareness activities about the presence of this aggressive invasive species, as early detection is essential to prevent plant invasions. Currently, breeding pressure from horticulture near sand dunes and coastal cliffs is the most important problem that needs to be addressed and resolved to prevent the further spread of *C. edulis* in coastal habitats along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author’ contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Chavdar Gussev: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Magdalena Valcheva: conceptualisation,

data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Bogdan Prodanov: data curation, investigation, validation, visualisation, writing—review and editing.

References

- Acosta A., Carranza M.L., Di Martino L., Frattaroli A., Izzi C.F., Stanisci A. 2008 Patterns of native and alien plant species occurrence on coastal dunes in Central Italy. In: Tokarska-Guzik B., Brock J.H., Brundu G., Child L., Daehler C.C., Pišek P. (eds) *Plant Invasions: Human Perception, Ecological Impacts and Management*. Backhuys, Leiden, The Netherlands, 235–248.
- Alados C.L., Pueyo Y., Barrantes O., Escós J., Giner L., Robles A.B. 2004 Variations in landscape patterns and vegetation cover between 1957 and 1994 in a semiarid Mediterranean ecosystem. *Landscape Ecology* 19: 543–559.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/B:LAND.0000036149.96664.9a>
- Andreu J., Manzano-Piedras E., Bartomeus I., Dana E.D., Vilà, M. 2010 Vegetation Response after Removal of the Invasive *Carpobrotus* Hybrid Complex in Andalucía, Spain. *Ecological Restoration* 28 (4): 440–448.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/43443292>
- Asensi A., Díez-Garretas B., Pereña J. 2016 Alien plants of coastal dune habitats in southern Spain. *Plant Biosystems* 150: 477–483.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2014.973463>
- Cabello J. 2009 Aizoaceae. In: Blanca G., Cabezudo B., Cueto M., Fernández López C., Morales Torres C. (eds) *Flora Vascular de Andalucía Oriental*, II vols. Sevilla, Consejería de Medio ambiente, Junta de Andalucía, 180–185.
- Campos J.A., Herrera M., Biurrun I., Loidi J. 2004 The role of alien plants in the natural coastal vegetation in central-northern Spain. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 13: 2275–2293.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/B:BIOC.0000047902.27442.92>
- Campoy J.G., Acosta A.T.R., Affre L., Barreiro R., Brundu G., Buisson E., González L., Lema M., Novoa A., Retuerto R., Roiloa S.R., Fagundez J.

- 2018 Monographs of invasive plants in Europe: *Carpobrotus*. Botany Letters 165: 440–475.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23818107.2018.1487884>
- Carboni M., Santoro R., Acosta A. 2010 Are some communities of the coastal dune zonation more susceptible to alien plant invasion? Journal of Plant Ecology 3: 139–147.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jpe/rtp037>
- Carranza M.L., Carboni M., Feola S., Acosta A.T.R. 2010 Landscape-scale patterns of alien plant species on coastal dunes: the case of iceplant in central Italy. Applied Vegetation Science 13: 135–145.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-109X.2009.01065.x>
- Conser C., Connor E.F. 2009 Assessing the residual effects of *Carpobrotus edulis* invasion, implications for restoration. Biological Invasions 11: 349–358.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-008-9252-z>
- Cullen J. 2011 *Carpobrotus*. In: Cullen J., Kness S.G., Cubey H.S. (eds) The European Garden Flora: Flowering Plants, 71, III vols. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 640.
- Davey F. H. 1909 Flora of Cornwall. Chegwiddden, Penryn.
- Defeo O., McLachlan A., Schoeman D.S., Schlacher T.A., Dugan J., Jones A., Lastra M., Scapini F. 2009 Threats on sandy beach ecosystems: A review. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science 81: 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2008.09.022>
- Delbaere B.C.W. 1998 Facts and Figures on European Biodiversity; State and Trends 1998–1999. European Centre for Nature Conservation: Tilburg, The Netherlands, 115.
- Doody J.P. 2013 Sand Dune Conservation, Management and Restoration. Springer, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 303.
- Drius M., Bongiorno L., Depellegrin D., Menegon S., Pugnetti A., Stifter S. 2019a Tackling challenges for Mediterranean sustainable coastal tourism: An ecosystem service perspective. Science of the Total Environment 652: 1302–1317.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.121>
- Drius M., Jones L., Marzialesetti F., de Francesco M.C., Stanisci A., Carranza M.L. 2019b Not just a sandy beach. The multi-service value of Mediterranean coastal dunes. Science of the Total Environment 668: 1139–1155.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019b.02.364>
- Gaertner M., Den Breeyen A., Hui C., Richardson D.M. 2009 Impacts of alien plant invasions on species richness in Mediterranean-type ecosystems: A meta-analysis. Progress in Physical Geography 33: 319–338.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133309341607>
- Giulio S., Cao Pinna L., Carboni M., Marzialesetti F., Acosta A.T.R. 2021 Invasion success on European coastal dunes. Plant Sociology 58 (1): 29–39.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/pls2021581/02>
- Gonçalves M.L. 1990 *Carpobrotus* N. E. Br. In: Castroviejo S., Lainz M., López González G., Montserrat P., Muñoz Garmendia F., Paiva J., Villar L. (eds) Flora Iberica, II vols. C.S.I.C., Madrid, 82–85.
- Haller I., Stybel N., Schumacher S., Mossbauer M. 2011 Will beaches be enough? Future challenges on coastal tourism at the German Baltic Sea. Journal of Coastal Research 61: 70–80.
- Hartmann H.E. (ed.) 2002 Illustrated handbook of succulent plants: Aizoaceae FZ (Vol. 2). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Hartmann H.E.K. 1993 Aizoaceae. In: Kubitzki K., Rohrer J.G., Bittrich V. (eds) The Families and Genera of Vascular Plants. Flowering Plants – Dicotyledons. Magnoliid, Hamamelid and Caryophyllid Families. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 37–69.
- Hesp P.A., Martínez M.L. 2007 Disturbance processes and dynamics in coastal dunes. In: Johnson E.A., Miyanishi K. (eds) Plant Disturbance Ecology: The Process and the Response. Elsevier/Academic Press, Cambridge, MA, USA, 215–247.
- Innangi M., Marzialesetti F., Di Febraro M., Acosta A.T.R., De Simone W., Frate L., Finizio M., Villalobos Perna P., Carranza M.L. 2023 Coastal Dune Invaders: Integrative Mapping of *Carpobrotus* sp. pl. (Aizoaceae) Using UAVs. Remote Sensing 15 (2): 503.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15020503>
- Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats – EUR28 2013 European Commission, DG Environment, Nature ENV B.3.
- Janssen J., Rodwell J., García Criado M., Gubbay S., Haynes T., Nieto A., Sanders N., Landucci F., Loidi

- J., Ssymank A., Tahvanainen T., Valderrabano M., Acosta A.T.R., Aronsson M., Arts G., Attorre F., Bergmeier E., Bijlsma R.-J., Bioret F., Biță-Nicolae C., Biurrun I., Calix M., Capelo J., Čarni A., Chytrý M., Dengler J., Dimopoulos P., Essl F., Gardfjell H., Gigante D., Giusso del Galdo G., Hájek M., Jansen F., Jansen J., Kapfer J., Mickolajczak A., Molina J.A., Molnár Z., Paternoster D., Piernik A., Poulin B., Renaux B., Schaminée J., Šumberová K., Toivonen H., Tonteri T., Tsiripidis I., Tzonev R., Valachovič M. 2016 European Red List of Habitats – Part 2 Terrestrial and freshwater habitats. European Union.
<https://doi.org/10.2779/091372>
- Jucker T., Carboni M., Acosta A.T.R. 2013 Going beyond taxonomic diversity: deconstructing biodiversity patterns reveals the true cost of iceplant invasion. *Diversity and Distributions* 19: 1566–1577.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12124>
- Kavrakova V., Dimova D., Dimitrov M., Tzonev R., Belev T., Rakovska K. 2009 Rakovodstvo za opredelyane na mestoobitania ot evropeyska znachimost v Bulgaria. World Wide Fund for Nature, Danube-Carpathian Program and federation “Zeleni Balkani”, Sofia, 131. (In Bulgarian)
- Lousley J.E. 1971 Flora of the Isles of Scilly. David and Charles, Newton Abbot.
- Mack R., Simberloff D., Lonsdale W.M., Evans H., Clout M., Bazzaz F.A. 2000 Biotic invasions: Causes, epidemiology, global consequences and control. *Ecological Applications* 10: 689–710.
[https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(2000\)010\[0689:BICEGC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(2000)010[0689:BICEGC]2.0.CO;2)
- Malavasi M., Santoro R., Cutini M., Acosta A.T.R., Carranza L. 2014 The impact of human pressure on landscape patterns and plant species richness in Mediterranean coastal dunes. *Plant Biosystems* 150 (1): 73–82.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2014.913730>
- Malavasi M., Santoro R., Cutini M., Acosta A.T.R., Carranza M.L. 2013 What has happened to coastal dunes in the last half century? A multitemporal coastal landscape analysis in Central Italy. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 119: 54–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2013.06.012>
- Manning J. 2018 Field guide to fynbos. Penguin Random House, South Africa.
- Marloth R. 1913 The Flora of South Africa, I vols. Darter Bros, Capetown.
- McClintock D. 1975 The Wild Flowers of Guernsey: With Notes of the Frequencies of All Species Recorded for the Channel Islands. Collins, London.
- Mifsud S. 2021 Morphology of the invasive *Carpobrotus* (Aizoaceae) in Europe: Malta as a case study. *Mediterranean Botany* 42: e71195.
<https://doi.org/10.5209/mbot.71195>
- Mucina L., Adams J., Knevel I., Rutherford M., Powrie L., Bolton J., van der Merwe J., Anderson R., Bornman T., le Roux A., Janssen J. 2006 Coastal Vegetation of South Africa. *Strelitzia* 19: 658–583.
- Novoa A., González L. 2014a Impacts of *Carpobrotus edulis* (L.) NE Br. on the germination, establishment and survival of native plants: a clue for assessing its competitive strength. *PLoS One* 9 (9): e107557.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0107557>
- Novoa A., González L., Moravcová L., Pyšek P. 2013 Constraints to Native Plant Species Establishment in Coastal Dune Communities Invaded by *Carpobrotus edulis*: Implications for Restoration. *Biological Conservation* 164: 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.04.008>
- Novoa A., Rodríguez R., Richardson D., González L. 2014b Soil quality: a key factor in understanding plant invasion? The case of *Carpobrotus edulis* (L.) NE. Br. *Biological Invasions* 16: 429–443.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-013-0531-y>
- Ortiz D.G., Lumbreras E.L., Rosselló J.A. 2008 Flora alóctona suculenta valenciana: Aizoaceae y Portulacaceae. *Monografías De Bouteloa* 7: 1–68.
- Petrosillo I., Zurlini G., Corliano M.E., Zaccarelli N., Dadamo M. 2007 Tourist perception of recreational environment and management in a marine protected area. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 79: 29–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2006.02.017>
- Preston C.D., Sell P.D. 1988 The Aizoaceae Naturalized in the British Isles. *Watsonia* 17 (3): 217–245.
- Prodanov B., Gussev C., Sopotlieva D., Valcheva M., Bekova R., Baltakova A., Tzonev R., Popov J. 2025 A standard procedure for dune mapping

- along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast: an integrated approach combining UAS photogrammetry, geomorphological and phytocoenological surveys. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 12:1579724.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2025.1579724>
- Roiloa S.R. 2019 Clonal traits and plant invasiveness: the case of *Carpobrotus* NE Br.(Aizoaceae). *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 40: 125479.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2019.125479>
- Roiloa S.R., Rodríguez-Echeverría S., de la Pena E., Freitas H. 2010 Physiological integration increases the survival and growth of the clonal invader *Carpobrotus edulis*. *Biological Invasions* 12 (6): 1815-1823.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-009-9592-3>
- Roiloa S.R., Abalde S., Xu C.Y., López L. 2017 The effect of stolon fragmentation on the colonization of clonal invasive *Carpobrotus edulis* in a coastal dune system: a field test. *Plant Species Biology* 32: 460–465.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1442-1984.12157>
- Santoro R., Jucker T., Carboni M., Acosta A.T.R. 2012 Patterns of plant community assembly in invaded and non-invaded communities along a natural environmental gradient. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 23: 483–494.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2011.01372.x>
- Sarmati S., Conti L., Acosta A.T. 2019 *Carpobrotus acinaciformis* vs *Carpobrotus edulis*: Are there any differences in their impact on coastal dune plant biodiversity? *Flora* 257: 151422.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flora.2019.151422>
- Schlacher T., Dugan J., Schoeman D.S., Lastra M., Jones A., Scapini F., McLachlan A., Defeo O. 2007 Sandy beaches at the brink. *Diversity and Distributions* 13: 556–560.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2007.00363.x>
- Šilc U., Stešević D., Luković M., Čaković D. 2020 Changes of a sand dune system and vegetation between 1950 and 2015 on Velika plaža (Montenegro, E Mediterranean). *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 35: 101139.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2020.101139>
- Simberloff D., Martin J.L., Genovesi P., Maris V., Wardle D.A., Aronson J., Courchamp F., Galil B., García-Berthou E., Pascal M., Pyšek P., Sousa R., Tabacchi E., Vilà M. 2013 Impacts of biological invasions: what's what and the way forward. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 28: 58–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2012.07.013>
- Strid A., Tan K. 1997 *Carpobrotus*. In: Strid A., Tan K. (eds) *Flora Hellenica I*. Koeltz Scientific Books, Königsten.
- Suehs C., Affre L., Médail F. 2004a Invasion dynamics of two alien *Carpobrotus* (Aizoaceae) taxa on a Mediterranean island: I. Genetic diversity and introgression. *Heredity* 92: 31–40.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.hdy.6800374>
- Suehs C.M., Affre L., Médail F. 2004b Invasion dynamics of two alien *Carpobrotus* (Aizoaceae) taxa on a Mediterranean island: II. Reproductive strategies. *Heredity* 92 (6): 550–556.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.hdy.6800454>
- Traveset A., Moragues E., Valladares F. 2008 Spreading of the invasive *Carpobrotus* aff. *acinaciformis* in Mediterranean ecosystems: the advantage of performing in different light environments. *Applied Vegetation Science* 11: 45–55.
<https://doi.org/10.3170/2007-7-18303>
- Tzonev R. 2015a Black Sea embryonic dunes. Red Data Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Natural Habitats. BAS & MoEW, Sofia, Bulgaria.
<http://e-ecodb.bas.bg/rdb/en/vol3/02B1.html>
- Tzonev R. 2015b Vegetation on the Black Sea sand beaches. Red Data Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Natural Habitats. BAS & MoEW, Sofia, Bulgaria.
<http://e-ecodb.bas.bg/rdb/en/vol3/01B1.html>
- Valcheva M., Sopotlieva D., Apostolova I., Tsvetkova N. 2021 Vegetation Characteristics and Recent Successional Trends of Sand Dune Habitats at the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast. *Coasts* 1: 1–24.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/coasts1010001>
- Van Dijk H.W.J. 1989 Ecological Impact of Drinking-water Production in Dutch Coastal Dunes. In: van der Meulen F., Jungerius P.D., Visser J., (eds) *Perspectives in Coastal Dune Management: Proceedings of the European Symposium Leiden*. SPB Academic Publishing, Hague, The Netherlands, 163–182.
- Varone L., Catoni R., Bonito A., Gini E., Gratani L. 2017 Photochemical performance of *Carpobrotus edulis* in response to various substrate salt concentrations. *South African Journal of Botany* 111: 258–266.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2017.03.035>

- Velev S. 2002 Climatic regioning. In: Koprarev I. (ed.) Geography of Bulgaria. Publishing House ForCom, Sofia, Bulgaria, 155–156.
- Vilà M., Tessier M., Suehs C.M., Brundu G., Carta L., Galanidis A., Lambdon P., Manca M., Médail F., Moragues E., Traveset A., Troumbis A.Y., Hulme P.E. 2006 Local and regional assessments of the impacts of plant invaders on vegetation structure and soil properties of Mediterranean islands. *Journal of Biogeography* 33: 853–861.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2005.01430.x>
- Weber E., D’Antonio C.M. 1999 Germination and growth responses of hybridizing *Carpobrotus* species (Aizoaceae) from coastal California to soil salinity. *American Journal of Botany* 86 (9): 1257–1263.
- Wisura W., Glen H.F. 1993 The South African species of *Carpobrotus* (Mesembryanthema-Aizoaceae). *Contributions to the Bolus Herbarium*, vol. 15: 76–107.
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